

THE FLAVONOIDS AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF *DAUCUS SYRTICUS* GROWING IN LIBYA

^{*1,3}Khaled A. Abdel Shafeek, ²Ali. M. Elsoll, ¹Hamid M. Younis, ¹Fatima M. AbdAlla, and ³Wael. M. ELsayed

¹Sirt University, Faculty of Science, Chemistry Department, Sirt, Libya , P. O. 674

²Musrata University, Faculty of Science, Chemistry Department, Musrata, Libya.

³Chemistry of medicinal plants dept., National Research Centre, Cairo, Egypt.

Article Received on 25 October 2013,

Revised on 23 November 2013,

Accepted on 28 December 2013

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20131674>

*Correspondence for

Author:

Dr. Khaled A. Abdel Shafeek

Sirt University, Faculty of Science, Chemistry

Department, Sirt, Libya .

khabdelhady@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Daucus syrticus is a wild plant common in the central zone of Libya, especially in Sirt region. Investigation of the flavonoidal constituents led to isolation and identification of three compounds from ethyl acetate fraction as: Luteolin, 7,4'- dimethoxy Luteolin and 6-hydroxy 4'-methoxy Apigenin. While Diosmetin-7-*O*-glucoide, Luteolin 3'- *O*-glucoside and 4'-methoxy Luteolin 7-*O*-rhamno-arabinoside were isolated from the butanol fraction of the methanolic extract . The structures of these flavonoids were characterized on the basis of their UV, NMR and MS spectroscopic data. The antimicrobial activity of different extracts and some of these compounds were tested against different microorganisms (bacteria and fungi). The results exhibited different degrees of inhibition against the tested microorganism.

Key words: *Apiaceae*, *Daucus syrticus*, flavonoidal and antimicrobial activity.

INTRODUCTION

Daucus is a genus of herbaceous plants belongs to family *Apiaceae* (*Umbelliferae*). It is a large family with about 300 genera and more than 3000 species ^[1]. Members of family *Apiaceae* are well to have several interesting biological activities, such as analgesic, , antibacterial, antiviral, anticoagulant, in addition to their well known photosensitizing effect^[2]. The family includes some highly toxic plants, such as hemlock. Many plants in this family, such as wild carrot, have estrogenic properties and have been used as folk medicine for birth control ^[3-4]. The ethnobotanical uses of plants of this genus include applications in

the treatment of cough, diarrhea, dysentery, cancer, malaria and tumors, and as an antiseptic, abortifacient, aphrodisiac, carminative, stimulant, stomachic and tonic^[5-7]. The pharmacological studies of *D. carota* have demonstrated the antibacterial^[8], antifungal^[9], anthelmintic, hepatoprotective^[10] and cytotoxic activities^[11]. The sesquiterpene (torilin) was isolated from *D. carota*. which was reported to possess antimicrobial^[12], anti-invasive^[13], anti-angiogenic^[14], analgesic and anti-inflammatory^[15] activities, along with the effects of inhibiting testosterone 5 α -reductase^[16]. The major isolated flavonoidal constituents were Kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside, Quercetin-3-*O*-glucoside, Apigenin-7-*O*-glucoside^[17], Luteolin-4'-sulph-ate^[18], Luteolin-7-*O*-(6"-*O*-malonyl)- β -D-glucopyranoside^[19], Luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside^[20], Skolimosite^[21], Apigenin and Luteolin^[22]. The main components in the essential oil of the flowers and fruits of *Daucus carota L. subsp. carota* and *Daucus carota L. subsp. Gummifer* were α - pinene, sabinene, limonene, β -pinene, myrcene, terpinene-4-ol, caryophyllene oxide, spathulenol, p-cymene and isospathulenol^[23]. The main components in the essential oil of the flowers and fruits of *D. carota*^[24-25] were α - pinene, sabinene, myrcene, limonene and three monoterpene alcohols (geraniol, nerol and carotol). The four guaiane derivatives (torilolone, torilin, 1 β -hydroxytorilin and 1 α -hydroxytorilin and one eudesmane type (voleneol). were isolated from *D. carota* by Hong *et. al.* in 2010^[21]. The aim of this study is the isolation, identification of the flavonoids and investigation of antimicrobial activity of some extracts and compounds from *Daucus syrticus* growing in Libya.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

The herb of *D. syrticus* was collected from Wadi Telal, Sirt region Libya, in January 2011, the plant was, kindly, identified by Dr. ElSayed Nafa, Botany Department, Faculty of Science, Sirt University, Sirt, Libya.

Instruments

- 1- UV viewing lamp at short and long wave length.
- 2- UV- Vis spectrophotometer 2401Schimadzu.
- 3- Bruker NMR spectrometer operating at 300 MHz for ¹H and 75 MHz for ¹³C NMR in DMSO.
- 4- Mass spectrometer JEOL JMS-AX 500.

Chemicals for chromatography

Solvents are , S1;butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5, upper layer), S2; ethyl acetate : formic acid : acetic acid : water (30 : 0.8 : 1.2 : 8), S3;15 % AcOH, S4; EtOAc : pyridine : H₂O (12 : 5 : 4), S5;butanol : acetic acid : water (3 : 1 : 1) and S6;10 % AcOH, Sephadex LH-20 for Column Chromatography, Pharmacia, polyamide (65 Riedel – de Haen for column chromatography).

Extraction, Purification and Isolation of flavonoids

About 1500 g of the dried powdered plant of *D. syrticus* herb were extracted with petroleum ether in a soxhlet apparatus. The defatted plant material (1400 g) were macerated with (90%) methanol till exhaustion. The alcoholic extract was evaporated in *vacuo* at about 50 °C . the obtained residue (50 g) was dissolved in hot distilled water 500 ml, left overnight in refrigerator and then filtered. The aqueous filtrate was extracted with successive portions of ethyl acetate (4×400 ml) followed by butanol (5×400 ml). The solvents were dried; separately; over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated in *vacuo* at about 50 °C. The ethyl acetate and butanol free residues amounted to be 6.2 g and 7.1 g respectively.

About 5 g of ethyl acetate extract were dissolved in 5 ml of methanol : water (80: 20) and applied on the top of a sephadexLH-20 (swollen in water) column. Elution was affected with methanol : water (80: 20) with decreasing the polarity. Fractions 150 ml each were collected and the course of chromatographic fractionation was followed by paper chromatography (whatmann 1 mm) in S3 as a developing solvent. The fraction 8-15 containing compound-1 were collected and further purified over a small Sephadex column, eluted with methanol : water (80: 20) and collecting fractions containing compound- 1 in pure form by (PC, S3 and S5). The solvent was evaporated in *vacuo* till dryness at 45 °C to give an amorphous yellow powder (49mg). The fractions 21-23 were collected and rechromatographed on a small Sephadex LH-20 column, eluted with methanol : water (80: 20) to give compound- 2 in pure form. The solvent was evaporated in *vacuo* till dryness at 45 °C (8.5mg). The fractions 24-28 were collected and rechromatographed on a small Sephadex LH20, column, eluted with methanol : water (80: 20) to give compound-3 in impure form. So, the compound was dissolvent in few ml of 95% methanol and applied on chromatographic papers as bands the paper were developed with S6, and the main compound was eluted with 90%,The solvent was evaporated in *vacuo* till dryness at 45 °C. to give compound-3 in pure form (25 mg).

About 6.5 g of butanol extract were dissolved in methanol and mixed with 5 g polyamide, The methanol was evaporated in *vacuo* at 45 °C till dryness to give a homogenous powdered

extract. This powder was transferred to polyamide column packed as a slurry in distilled water. Elution started with 100 % distilled water and after then the polarity was decreased by addition methanol till 100% methanol. Fractions of each polarity (one L) were collected. The chromatographic fractionation was monitored using PC and 15 % acetic acid as a developing solvent. The fraction 6 eluted with Methanol : Water (80: 20) was found to contain one main compound ($R_f = 0.33$) so, further purified using polyamide column eluted with Methanol : Water (80: 20). The eluted fractions containing compound- 4 ($R_f = 0.33$) in semi pure form (PC, S3 and S5) were collected and after then, the compound was passed over a small sephadex column eluted with 80 % methanol, the fractions containing compound-4 in pure form were collected and the solvent evaporated in *vacuo* at 40 °C. to give a yellowish powder (45.2 mg). The fraction 7 eluted with Methanol : Water (90: 10) was found to contain more than one compound with main one ($R_f = 0.48$) so, they collected and further purified using small polyamide column eluted with Methanol : Water (90: 10). The eluted fractions containing compound- 5 ($R_f = 0.48$) in pure form (PC, S3 and S5) were collected and the solvent was evaporated in *vacuo* at 40 °C (33.6 mg). The fraction 9 containing compound-6 was further purified over a small polyamide column eluted with Methanol 100% and collecting small fractions (25 ml each). The fractions containing compound-6 (PC, S3 and S5, $R_f = 0.68$) were collected and the solvent was evaporated in *vacuo* at 40 °C it was found that the compound is also not pure so, was subjected to PPC (Watmmann 3mm) using 15 % acetic acid as a developing solvent (two runs). The pure compound-6 was collected (9.8 mg) and it's purity was checked by 2DPC in different solvents.

Antimicrobial activity study

Preparation of different extracts for antimicrobial activity studies

About 100 g of the air dried powdered plant were extracted firstly with methanol for 24 hours to afford methanolic extract which partitioned with chloroform, ethyl acetate and butanol respectively and the mother liquor was tested as ML. Five concentrations were prepared from each extract as a, b, c, d and f which are 50, 100, 150, 200, 250 µg / ml respectively.

Biological experiments

The antimicrobial activity was evaluated using micro dilution method, in which minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) determination was performed. The extracts were tested against a panel of micro organisms including bacteria (Gram positive Gram negative),

yeasts and fungi according to the methods described by Cowan in 1999^[26] and Jin *et. al.* in 2004^[27].

Maintenance of the microorganism

The microorganisms used in the current work were obtained from Natural and Microbial products chemistry department, National research center, Dokki, Cairo Egypt. The used bacterial species were maintained on nutrient agar medium at 37 °C potato dextrose agar (PDA) was used for fungi. After 12 h of activation, bacterial suspensions were made and this turbidity was standardized, by estimation of the optical density on spectrophotometer [UV-VIS, 1610 Shimadzu, Tokyo, Japan]. The final density of bacteria 1×10^6 cell/ml and 1×10^5 respectively. On the other hand, the fungal strain was used after 3 day of incubation was diluted using saline to give 1×10^4 spore/ml.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The flavonoids of *D. syrticus* were isolated from the ethyl acetate and butanol fractions of alcoholic extract. Six flavonoids were identified as follow:-

1-Luteolin: The compound was isolated as a yellow powder and its chromatographic behavior proved it is an aglycone in nature. Its UV absorption spectra in methanol showed band- I at 349 nm (flavone type) in addition to a bathochromic shift in band- I with NaOMe (53 nm) with increasing intensity, indicates the presence of a free OH group at C- 4'. The AlCl₃ spectrum showed a bathochromic shift in band- I (60 nm) relative to methanol spectrum indicates the presence of a free OH group at C-5. The presence of an *ortho*-dihydroxy system in ring- B was confirmed, where, there is a hypsochromic shift (39 nm) in band- I in AlCl₃ / HCl spectrum relative to AlCl₃ spectrum. Also it was proved through NaOAc / H₃BO₃ spectrum, where, there is a bathochromic shift (27 nm) in band- I relative to the methanol spectrum. The NaOAc spectrum showed a bathochromic shift (17nm) in band- II indicating the presence of free OH group at C- 7. The EI- mass spectrum showed a molecular ion peak at $m/z = 286$ (M^+ ; 82 %) which corresponding to the molecular formula C₁₅H₁₀O₆. Another important peaks at $m/z = 287$ ($M^+ + 1$; 91 %) and 258 ($M^+ - CO$, 20 %). The fragmentation pathway of that compound undergoes Retero Diel's Alder reaction (RDAR) giving rise to fragments at $m/z = 153$ ($A^+ + 1$; 35 %), 134 ($B^+ + 1$; 20.6 %). The ¹H-NMR spectrum (DMSO) showed signals at δ in ppm 7.38 (2H, d, $J = 1.8$ Hz, H- 2',6'), 6.89 (1H, d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H- 5'), 6.64 (1H, s, H- 3), 6.44 (1H, d, $J = 3$ Hz, H- 8), 6.15 (1H, d, $J =$

3 Hz, H- 6) which are in agreement with those reported for luteolin ^[28]. All these data were coincided with that reported for luteolin.

2- 7, 4'-dimethoxy Luteolin: The UV absorption spectra in methanol showed band- I at 340 nm (flavone type) in addition to a bathochromic shift in band- I with NaOMe (40 nm) with decreasing in intensity indicates the absence of a free OH group at C- 4'. The AlCl₃ spectrum showed a bathochromic shift in band- I (42 nm) relative to methanol spectrum indicates the presence of a free OH group at C-5. The absence of an *ortho*- dihydroxy system was proved through AlCl₃ / HCl spectrum as there is no hypsochromic shift in band- I was occur relative to AlCl₃ spectrum. Also, no hypsochromic shift in band- I was observed in NaOAc / H₃BO₃ spectrum relative to the methanol spectrum. The absence of a free OH group at C- 7 was confirmed because there is no bathochromic shift in band- II of NaOAc spectrum. The EI-mass spectrum showed a molecular ion peak at m/z = 316 (M⁺; 9 %) which corresponding to the molecular formula C₁₇H₁₄O₆. Another important peaks at m/z = 300 (M⁺- CH₂; 12 %), 285 (M⁺- 2 CH₃; 100 %) and 258 (M⁺- [2 CH₃ + CO]; 30 %).The fragmentation pathway of the compound undergoes Retero Diel's Alder reaction (RDAR) giving rise to fragments at m/z =153 ((A⁺₁ +1); 45 %), 134(B⁺₁; 12 %). From the above chromatographic and spectroscopic data compound- 2 can be identified as :7, 4'- dimethoxy Luteolin.

3- 6-hydroxy-4'-methoxy Apigenin: The UV absorption spectra in methanol and other shift reagents proved that, the compound is a flavones in nature with free OH groups at carbon atoms 5, 6 and 7exhibited in addition to methoxy group at C4'. The EI- mass spectrum of compound- 3 showed a molecular ion peak at m/z = 300 (M⁺; 100 %) which corresponding to the molecular formula C₁₆H₁₂O₆. Another important peaks at m/z = 270 [M⁺- (OH+CH₃); 31%], and 257 [M⁺- (CH₃ + CO); 11.5 %]. The fragmentation pathway of the compound undergoes Retero Diel's Alder reaction (RDAR) giving rise to fragments at m/z =153 ((A⁺₁ +1); 21 %), 118 (B⁺₁; 4 %). The ¹H- NMR spectrum (DMSO) showed signals at δ in ppm 7.38 (2H, d, J= 8.5 Hz, H- 2',6'), 6.93 (2H,d, J= 9 Hz, H- 5',3'), 6.64 (1H, s, H- 3), 6.20 (1H, d, J= 3.5 Hz, H- 8) , and 3.90 (3H,s,C-4') ^[29]. From the above chromatographic and spectroscopic data compound- 3 can be identified as: 6-hydroxy 4'-methoxy Apigenin.

4- Diosmetin7-O –glucoside: The chromatographic behavior of the compound in different solvent systems proved that it is a glycoside in nature. The UV absorption spectrum in methanol proved that, the compound is a flavones type with free OH groups at carbon 3 and 5 while the occupation at C7 and C4'. The position of glycosidation was confirmed (after acid hydrolysis) at C7 where the aglycone exhibited a bathochromic shift in band- II relative to methanol spectrum in NaOAc spectrum indicating the presence of a free OH group at C-7.

The EI- mass spectrum showed a molecular ion peak at $m/z = 462$ (M^+ ; 5.3 %) which corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{22}H_{22}O_{11}$. The presence of peaks at $m/z = 300$ (100%) indicates the sugar is a hexose moiety ($M^+ - 162$). Another important fragment at $m/z 285$ (5%), $m/z 257$ (12%), $m/z = 153$ ($(A_1^+ + 1)$; 19%), and 148 ((B_1^+) ; 11%). From this fragmentation pathway we can say that the methoxy group was present at C-4' in ring - B. The 1H - NMR spectrum (DMSO) showed signals at δ in ppm 7.56 (2H, d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H- 2',6'), 6.97 (1H, d, $J = 8$ Hz, H- 5'), 6.91 (1H, s, H- 3), 6.84 (1H, d, $J = 3.5$ Hz, H- 8), 6.41 (1H, d, $J = 3.5$ Hz, H- 6) and 3.87 (3H, s, OCH_3 -C4'), The anomeric proton of glucose appears as a sharp signal at $\delta = 5.04$ (1H, d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H-1'') which are in agreement with those reported for Diosmetin-7-O -glucoside^[30]. Only diosmetin and glucose were identified after acid hydrolysis. From all the above chromatographic and spectroscopic data compound- 4 can be identified as: Diosmetin-7-O -glucoside.

5- Luteolin 3'- O- glucoside: The compound appeared as a dull spot under the UV light which changed into yellow spot after exposure to ammonia and it becomes a greenish yellow after spraying with $AlCl_3$ solution. The UV absorption spectra of the compound- 5 in methanol showed band- I at 348nm (flavone type) in addition to a bathochromic shift band- I with NaOMe (30 nm) with increasing in intensity, indicates the presence of a free OH group at C- 4'. The $AlCl_3$ spectrum showed a bathochromic shift in band- I (33nm) relative to methanol spectrum indicates the presence of a free OH group at C- 5. The $AlCl_3 / HCl$ spectrum showed no hypsochromic shift in band- I relative to $AlCl_3$ spectrum which prove the absence of an *ortho*- dihydroxy system, which was confirmed through the NaOAc / H_3BO_3 spectrum. The NaOAc spectrum showed bathochromic shift (10nm) in band- II indicating the presence of free OH group at C- 7. The EI- mass spectrum of compound- 5 displayed a molecular ion peak M^+ at $m/z = 449$ ($M + 1$; 10%) which calculated for the molecular formula ($C_{21}H_{20}O_{11} + 1$), the peaks at $m/z = 286$ ($M^+ - \text{hexose moiety}$; 100%) and 257 ($M^+ - [CO + \text{hexose moiety}]$; 5%) confirm the presence of hexose moiety. The fragmentation pathway of compound- 5 undergoes (RDAR) giving rise to fragments at $m/z 153$ ($A_1^+ + 1$; 5%) and 134 (B_1^+ ; 12.5%). The 1H - NMR spectrum showed signals at δ in ppm 7.48 (2H, d, $J = 7.3$ Hz, H- 2',6'), 7.2 (1H, d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, H- 5'), 6.81 (1H, s, H- 3), 6.48 (1H, d, $J = 3$ Hz, H- 8) and 6.18 (1H, d, $J = 3.5$ Hz, H- 6), The anomeric proton of glucose appears as a sharp signal at $\delta = 4.86$ (1H, d, $J = 8$ Hz, H-1'')^[31]. After the acid hydrolysis luteolin was identified as an aglycone and glucose as a sugar and the UV of the aglycone proved the presence of an *ortho* dihydroxy system which confirm the position of

glycosidation of the sugar is at C3', so these data were in accordance with that reported for Luteolin 3'- O- glucoside.

6- 4'-methoxy luteolin 7-O-rhamno-arabinoside: The compound was isolated as a morphus powder and appereaed as a brown spot changed into yellowish after spraying with AlCl₃. It's UV absorption spectra in methanol showed band- I at 344nm (flavone type) in addition to a bathochromic shift band- I with NaOMe (57 nm) with decrease in intensity which indicates the absence of a free OH group at C-4'. The AlCl₃ spectrum showed a bathochromic shift in band-I (33nm) relative to methanol spectrum indicates the presence of a free OH group at C-5. The AlCl₃ / HCl spectrum showed no hypsochromic shift in band- I relative to AlCl₃ spectrum which prove the absence of an *ortho*- dihydroxy system, which was confirmed through the NaOAc / H₃BO₃ spectrum. The NaOAc spectrum showed no bathochromic shift in band- II relative to methanol spectrum indicating the absence of a free OH group at C-7. The EI- mass spectrum displayed a molecular ion peak M⁺ at m/z = 578 (M ; 5 %) which calculated for the molecular formula (C₂₇ H₃₀ O₁₄), The presence of a peaks at m/z = 300 (100 %) indicates the sugar is (deoxyhexose with pentose moiety) [M⁺ - (146+132)]. There are Another important fragments at m/z = 272 (6%) , m/z = 257 (17%).The fragmentation pathway of compound- 6 undergoes (RDAR) giving rise to fragments at m/z 153 (15 %), m/z 150 (5 %) and 148(10 %). The acid hydrolysis proved the presence of luteolin as an aglycone , in addition to rhamnose and arabinose as sugars. The position of the attachement of the two sugars was confirmed at C-7 through the UV spectrum of the aglycone in NaOAc. All the above data substantiated that compound- 6 can be identified as : 4' -methoxy luteolin 7-O-rhamno- arabinoside.

NO	Compound	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6
1	luteolin	H	H	H	H	OH	OH
2	7, 4'- dimethoxy Luteolin	H	CH ₃	H	H	OH	OCH ₃
3	6-hydroxy 4'-methoxy Apigenin.	H	OH	OH	H	H	OCH ₃
4	Diosmetin7-O –glucoside	H	glucose	H	H	OH	OCH ₃
5	Luteolin 3'- O- glucoside	H	H	H	H	O-glucose	OH
6	4'-methoxyluteolin7-O-rhamno- arabinoside.	H	rham- arabinose	H	H	OH	OCH ₃

Table (1): Antimicrobial activity of different extracts of *D. syrticus*.

Extract con	Conc.	Microbes			
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
		MIC with Inhibition zone in cm			
Chloroform	a	0.6	0.7		
	b	0.9	0.8		
	c	1.1	1.0	-	-
	d	1.4	1.1		
	e	1.4	1.1		
Ethyl acetate	a		-	-	-
	b		-	0.5	-
	c	-	0.5	0.5	0.5
	d		0.6	0.7	0.8
	e		0.6	0.7	0.8
Butanol	a	-	0.6		
	b	0.8	0.8		
	c	0.9	0.9	-	-
	d	0.9	1.2		
	e	0.9	1.2		
M. L.	a	0.7	-	-	-
	b	0.8	0.5	0.4	-
	c	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.4
	d	1.1	0.8	0.7	0.5
	e	1.1	0.8	0.7	0.5
Compound-1	a	-		-	
	b	0.4		0.8	
	c	0.5	-	1.0	-
	d	0.6		1.3	
	e	0.6		1.3	
Compound - 4	a		-		
	b		0.5		
	c	-	0.5	-	-
	d		0.7		
	e		0.7		

The scale of measurement was following (disk diameter is not included)

Antibacterial control is cephalexine in conc. 150 mg/ml (IZ =2.9 cm)

Antifungal control is nastatine in conc. 150 mg/ml (IZ= 3.1 cm)

Antimicrobial activity of *Daucus syrticus*

Investigation of antimicrobial activity of different extracts with different concentrations as a, b, c, d and f which are 50, 100, 150, 200 and 250 µg/ml respectively, using Disc diffusion modified by Kirby- Bauer and Streaking methods against some selected microorganisms (bacteria and fungus). The data in (Table 1) revealed the presence of different degrees of activity as follow, The chloroform extract had great activity towards Gram -ve but reduced effect against Gram +ve and yeast. The ethyl acetate extract had no effect on Gram -ve, bacteria, but had a reduced level on Gram +ve and yeast. The butanol extract had a remarkable effect against Gram -ve bacteria, but had no effect on yeast and fungus. The M. L. extract had great activity towards against Gram -ve , Gram +ve bacteria and low activity against yeast and fungus. It is also noted that, compound-1 (Luteolin) exhibited activity against *A. niger* and *E. coli*, while compound-4 (Diosmetin-7-O- glucoside) gave activity against *B. subtilis* only, this low activity may be due to lake of free OH groups , also it is clear that, the extracts is more effective than pure compounds which may be due to the synergism effect of different compounds in each extract.

REFERENCES

- 1- Sáenz, LC " Research on *Daucus L. (Apiaceae)*" *Anales Jardin Botanico De Madrid*, 1981; 37: 481–533, .
- 2- Mani, V and Milind, P "Pharmacological evidence for the potential of *Daucus carota* in the management of cognitive dysfunctions" *Biol. Pharm. Bull.* 2006; 29(6): 1154-1161.
- 3- Kritikar, KR and Basu, BD " Indian medicinal plants" 2nd ed., periodical export, New Delhi, India, 1991.
- 4- Mehdi, M; Maryam, Y; Zohreh, H and Abbas, S " Two new coumarins from the chloroform extract of *Angelica urumiensis* from Iran Chem" *Pharm. Bull.*, 2010; 58(4): 546-548.
- 5- Teubert, H; Wünscher, G; and Herrmann, K " Flavonols and flavones of vegetables" VIII. Flavones of carrot leaves. *Z. Lebensm Unters Forsch.*, 1977; 165(3):147-50.
- 6- Harborne, J. B. "Flavonoid and phenylpropanoid patterns in the *Umbelliferae*. The biology and chemistry of the *Umbelliferae*" Academic Press, London, Heywood, 11th ed.,1971; pp. 293, D314,
- 7- Jafri, I and El-Gadi, A " Flora of Libya" Al-Fateh publishing corporation, Illinois. university press, Tripoli, Libya, 1977, vol. 117: p. 136.
- 8- Ana Cristina, T; Maria, JG; Carlos, C ; Maria, TC ; Maria, CL ; Jorge, S and Ligia, RS

- "Essential oil of *Daucus carota* subsp. *Halophilus* Composition, antifungal activity and cytotoxicity" J. Ethnopharmacol., 2008; 199: 129-134.
- 9- Cho, WL.; Choi, JB; Lee, K; Chung, MS and Pyun, YR. "Antimicrobial activity of torillin isolated from *T. Japonica* fruit against *B. subtilis*" J. Food Sci., 2008;73: M37-46.
- 10- Kim, MS; Lee, YM; Moon. E; Kim, SE and Lee, JJ. "Antimutagenic activity of torilin" Int. J. Cancer, 2000; 87: 269.
- 11- Niko R, Nevenka D and Zorica S "volatiles of the Balkan endemic *D. guttatus* Ssp *zahariadii* and cultivated and wild – growing *D. carota* - A comparison study " Food Chem., 2011;125: 35-43.
- 12- Andrew, SP ; Shahrzad, F; Alexis, S; Bhimanagouda, SP and Farzad, D "Drinking carrot juice increases total antioxidant status and decreases lipid peroxidation in adults" J. Nutr., 2011; 10: 96.
- 13- Wageesha, ND; Ekanayajke, S; Jansz, E R and Lamabadusuriya S " Studies on hypercarotenemia due to excessive ingestion of carrot, pumpkin and papaw" Int. J. Food Sci. Nutr., 2011; 62(1): 20-25.
- 14- Roman, M; Dobrowolski, J C; Baranska, M and Baranski, K "Spectroscopic studies on bioactive polyacetylenes and other plant components in wild carrot root" J. Nat. Prod., 2011;74(8): 1757-63.
- 15- Zeinab, RA; Mroueh, M; Diab-Assaf, M; Jurjus, A; Wex, B; Sakr, A and Daher, CF "Chemopreventive effects of wild carrot oil against 7,12-dimethyl benz(a)anthracene-induced squamous cell carcinoma in mice" Pharm. Biol., 2011; 49(9): 955-61.
- 16- Halim, AF and Mansour S S "Isodaucoglabrin another triester phenylpropanoids from *Daucus glaber* Forssk. " Mans. J. pharm. Sci., 1990; 6: 32-39.
- 17- Amal, AS; Yukio, H; El- Sayeds , M; Atallah, FA; Sahar, G; Haruhiko, F and Koichi,T " phenylpropanoid triester from *Daucus glaber* Forssk. " phytochem. Letters, 2009; 2: 188-191 .
- 18- Diccarlo, G; Mascolo, N; Izzo, AA and Capasso, F "flavonoids old and new aspects of a class of natural therapeutic drugs" Life Sci., 1999; 65(4): 337-53.
- 19- Hong – Wei Fu.; Lin Zhang .; Tao Yi.; Yu – Lin Feng and Jing Kui Tian. "Two new Guaiane – Type sesquiterpenes Glycosids from the fruits of *Daucus carota* L" Chem. Pharm., 2010; 58 (1): 125- 128.

- 20- Hong – WF; Lin Z; Tao Y; Yu – Lin F and Jing – Kui T. " Guaiane type sesquiterpenes and other constituents from *D. carota* L. " Biochem. Syst. and Ecol., 2010; 38: 309- 312.
- 21- Garrod, B; Lewis, BG and Coxon, DT "The accumulation of inhibitory compounds in the induced resistance response of carrot root to *Botrytis cinerea*" physiol. Plant pathol., 1981;18: 7-15 .
- 22- Meliani, N; Dib, MA; Allali, H and Tabti, B "Comparative analysis of essential oil components of two *Daucus* species from Algeria and their antimicrobial activity" Int. Res. J. Biol. Sci. 2013; 2(1): 22-29.
- 23- Staniszewska, A and Kula, J "Composition of the essential oil from wild carrot umbels (*Daucus carota* L ssp. *carota*) growing in Poland" J. Essent. oil Res. 2001; 13: 439-441.
- 24- Halim, AF.; Mashaly, MM and Sandra, P "Analysis of the Fruit essential oil of *Daucus carota* L .var. *Boissieri schweinf* " 1st , Anglo- Egypton conference of pharm. Sci, Alexandria, Egypt, 1988; 15-17.
- 25- Cowan, MM "Plant products as antimicrobial agents" Clin. Microbiol. Rev. 1999; 12: 564-582.
- 26- Jin Hee, K.; Jung, S. and Seung, W. "The improvement of cephalosporin C. production by fed- batch culture of *Cephalosporium acremonium*" Biotechnol. and Bioprocen Eng., 2004; 9: 459-464.
- 27- Fusani, P and Zidorn, C " Phenolics and sesquiterpene lactone in the edible shots of *Cicerbita alpina* (L.) Wallroth" J. Food Comp. Anal.; 2010; 23: 658-663.
- 28- Peng, JY; Fan, GR and Wu, YT . Studies on chemical constituents of *Patrinia villosa*. Zhongguo Zhong Yao Za Zhi. 2006; 31(2): 128-30.
- 29- Matsuta, T; Sakagami, H; Satoh, K; Kannamoto, T; Terakubo, S; Nakashima, H; Kitajima, M; Oizumi, H and Oizumi, T "Biological activity of luteolin glycosides and tricrin from *Sasa senanensis* " In Vivo 2011; 25(5): 757-62.
- 30- Wang, Y J; Yang, XW and Guo, QS "Studies on chemical constituents in Huangjuhua (flowers of *Chrysanthemum morifolium*). Zhongguo Zhong Yao Za Zhi. 2008; 33(5): 526-30.